

ANALYSIS OF REGIONAL FEATURES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SUSTAINABLE TOURISM AND WAYS TO ADAPT THEM

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Abstract. *This article considers the role of PESTEL, SWOT and TOWS analyses in the development of sustainable tourism. PESTEL-analysis assesses the impact of political, economic, social, technological, environmental and legal factors on tourism. As a result of the conducted analyses, improving infrastructure, introducing digital technologies, strengthening environmental policy and increasing the participation of the local population were identified as important strategic directions.*

Keywords: *Sustainable tourism, PESTEL-analysis, SWOT-analysis, TOWS matrix, environmental sustainability, digital technologies.*

Introduction. In the modern world, the tourism industry is considered one of the most important sectors of the economy. In particular, the concept of sustainable tourism aims at long-term development goals through the efficient use of natural resources, the preservation of cultural heritage and the improvement of the well-being of the local population. For the development of sustainable tourism, a comprehensive analysis of external and internal factors is necessary. In this regard, PESTEL, SWOT and TOWS analyses play an important role.

The main objective of the study is to identify ways to apply and improve strategic analysis methods for the development of a sustainable tourism model. During the study, PESTEL, SWOT and TOWS analyses were used to analyze external and internal factors affecting sustainable tourism.

The results of the study allow us to develop recommendations for improving sustainable tourism from an infrastructural, environmental and technological perspective. The development of sustainable tourism depends on external factors, including political, economic, social, technological, environmental and legal aspects. PESTEL analysis helps to study these factors and assess their impact on the tourism industry. For example, government policies and tourism support programs directly affect the development of the tourism industry.

SWOT analysis allows you to identify the internal strengths and weaknesses of sustainable tourism, as well as external opportunities and threats. For example, the abundance of natural and cultural resources is one of the strengths, while weak environmental standards and insufficient infrastructure are weaknesses. In addition, opportunities for the development of ecotourism and threats such as climate change should also be taken into account. The TOWS matrix helps translate the results of the SWOT analysis into strategic decisions. This method allows you to propose strategies aimed at improving sustainable tourism by exploiting opportunities, mitigating threats, strengthening strengths and overcoming weaknesses..

This article presents strategies for the development of sustainable tourism, comprehensively considering PESTEL, SWOT and TOWS analyses. In particular, the importance of improving the sustainable tourism model by combining environmental, economic,

technological and social aspects is highlighted. Such an integrated approach allows for the effective management of natural resources, maintaining economic stability, introducing innovative solutions and taking into account the interests of local communities.

Literature review. Recent research on sustainable tourism in Kazakhstan highlights the importance of adapting models to local conditions. A minimal model approach with three variables – tourists, environment and capital – suggests that sustainable tourism can be achieved through prudent reinvestment and environmental protection [1]. The tourism capacity approach developed by Cifuentes in 1992 is essential for balancing tourist numbers with the environmental constraints of destinations. Innovative entrepreneurship, especially among young people, has been identified as a key driver of tourism sector growth [2]. In addition, intangible cultural heritage plays a key role in shaping sustainable tourism practices, highlighting the need for collaboration between government and non-governmental organizations and local communities to protect and promote this heritage [3]. These studies integrate the multifaceted approach needed to develop sustainable tourism models in Kazakhstan.

It highlights the importance of adapting sustainable tourism models to local conditions, especially in the context of climate change. Jopp et al. present a comprehensive framework for adapting regional destinations that takes into account supply and demand perspectives to enhance sustainability while exploiting opportunities [4]. Demonstrate the effectiveness of integrating climate change adaptation with local sustainability discourses through participatory decision-making processes in alpine winter tourism [5]. Mashnik’s study presents different models of ecotourism for protected areas, highlighting the importance of tourism relationships, local community participation and impact on education [6]. Pene highlights the need for models that encourage local community participation to reduce negative externalities and protect natural and cultural resources [7]. Collectively, these studies demonstrate the importance of adapting sustainable tourism approaches to specific local contexts, engaging stakeholders, and addressing the impacts of climate change, in order to ensure long-term viability and public benefits.

It examines various analytical tools for planning sustainable tourism development. SWOT analysis is a widely used approach to assess internal strengths and weaknesses, along with external opportunities and threats [8]. It provides an advanced SWOT model that includes global factors and action-oriented strategies. The PESTEL framework is another valuable tool for examining the political, economic, social, technological, environmental and legal factors that affect tourism development [9]. These analytical tools can be used in a variety of contexts, from rural areas to entire counties. They help identify key components of tourism, development opportunities and potential problems. By systematically assessing the internal and external environment, these tools support decision-making and the development of sustainable tourism development strategies [10].

Research methods This study used the PESTEL, SWOT and TOWS methods to conduct a strategic analysis for the development of sustainable tourism.

PESTEL analysis:

It was used to assess the political, economic, social, technological, environmental and legal factors that affect sustainable tourism; the impact of each factor was analyzed quantitatively and qualitatively, and the main trends were identified.

SWOT analysis:

It was used to identify internal strengths and weaknesses, as well as external opportunities and threats in the tourism industry; This analysis allowed us to assess the current state of sustainable tourism and identify ways to improve it.

TOWS matrix:

Based on the results of the SWOT analysis, specific strategic solutions were proposed; strategies for the development of sustainable tourism were developed by exploiting opportunities and mitigating threats.

1. PESTEL analysis: assessing the external factors of a sustainable tourism model

PESTEL analysis examines the political, economic, social, technological, environmental and legal factors that affect sustainable tourism.

Table-1. PESTEL analysis

Factor	Impact Level	Main characteristics
Political (P)	High	Government programs and support for ecotourism
Economic (E)	Medium	Development of tourism infrastructure and investment opportunities
Social (S)	High	Level of participation of local people in tourism, preservation of culture and traditions
Technological (T)	Medium	Level of digitization, smart tourism solutions
Ecological (E)	Low	Implementation of environmental standards, protection of natural areas
Legal (L)	Medium	Effectiveness and implementation of tourism-related laws

The PESTEL analysis shows that the sustainable tourism sector is moderately developed, but environmental and legal aspects need to be improved.

2. SWOT analysis: identifying internal strengths and weaknesses

A SWOT analysis assesses the internal strengths and weaknesses of sustainable tourism, as well as external opportunities and threats.

Table 2. SWOT analysis

Factors	Content
Strengths (S)	Rich natural resources, national cultural heritage, government support
Weaknesses (W)	Insufficient tourism infrastructure, weak environmental standards
Opportunities (O)	Local population activity, potential for ecotourism development
Threats (T)	Climate change, incomplete implementation of legislation

The SWOT analysis revealed the need to improve infrastructure and strengthen environmental policies for the development of sustainable tourism.

3. TOWS Matrix: Making Strategic Decisions

The TOWS Matrix helps to translate SWOT analysis into strategic decisions.

Table-3. TOWS Matrix

Factors	Use strengths (S)	Overcome weaknesses (W)
Opportunities (O)	Develop ecotourism, introduce digital services	Train local entrepreneurs, create grant programs
Threats (T)	Introduce environmental restrictions, develop a sustainable tourism model	Improve legislation, increase funding

Based on the TOWS matrix, the following strategies are proposed: environmental sustainability: strengthening environmental protection measures, introducing sustainable tourism standards; economic development: developing public-private partnerships, investment support; technological improvement: developing digital tourism platforms, introducing the smart tourism concept; social strategies: educating the local population, promoting cultural heritage; based on the analysis for the development of sustainable tourism, the following assumptions were made; strengthening environmental policy will contribute to the long-term development of sustainable tourism; increasing the volume of investment will improve tourism infrastructure and increase competitiveness.

Conclusion A comprehensive approach was used to develop sustainable tourism using PESTEL, SWOT and TOWS analyses. The results of the study showed that environmental sustainability, infrastructure improvement, the introduction of digital technologies and increasing the participation of the local population were identified as the main priority areas in the development of sustainable tourism. The following measures are recommended for the development of sustainable tourism in the future. The development of sustainable tourism requires long-term strategies. Therefore, success in the field of sustainable tourism can only be achieved if public policy, scientific research and innovation are coordinated.

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